

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

A HIGH THROUGHPUT LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY TANDEM-MASS SPECTROMETRY METHOD FOR THE QUANTIFICATION OF NAPROXEN SODIUM IN HUMAN PLASMA: APPLICATION TO PHARMACOKINETIC STUDY

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 30/06/2017

Available online

30/07/2017

Keywords

LCMS-MS Method,
Esipositiveionization Mode,
Naproxen Sodium,
Protein Precipitate Method,
Pharmacokinetic Study.

ABSTRACT

Background: A LCMS-MS method has been validated for the determination of naproxen using ketoprofen as an internal standard. **Methods:** Protein precipitate method was used to extract both analytes and internal standard from human plasma. Detection was made at m/z 229.1 / 169.0 for naproxen, m/z 253.08 / 209.0 for internal standard using esi positive ionization mode. Mass hunter 4.1 workstation software was used for the quantification. The stationary phase was Gemini C18, 50 x 4.6, 5 μ m. The optimum mobile phase was found to be acetonitrile and ammonium acetate buffer 20 mM (1:1 v/v). The separation was carried out by using temperature at 30°C (Degree centigrade) with a flow rate of 0.8 mL (milliliter). The injection volume was 5 μ L (microliter) and run time was 3 minutes. The retention time of analyte and internal standard was 2.054 and 1.922 minutes. **Results:** The method chosen is fast, robust, and sensitive. Each sample requires less than 3 min run time. The assay method is also highly specific due to the intrinsic selectivity of tandem mass spectrometry. The precision and accuracy are within the recommended limits in this concentration range. **Conclusion:** The developed method validated for accuracy, precision, linearity and recovery. The calibration curves were linear from 1.167 μ g/mL to 163.729 μ g/mL (microgram/milliliter) for naproxen. The validated technique has been effectively applied to analyze human plasma samples for application in pharmacokinetic studies.

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Please cite this article in press as **Ramesh N et al.** A High Throughput Liquid Chromatography Tandem–Mass Spectrometry Method for the Quantification of Naproxen Sodium in Human Plasma: Application to Pharmacokinetic Study. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(07).

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INTRODUCTION

Naproxen is a propionic acid derivative related to the aryl acetic acid group of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. Naproxen is a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug with analgesic and antipyretic properties. The sodium salt of naproxen has been established to have more rapid absorption [1-2]. The chemical names for naproxen and naproxen sodium are (S)-6-methoxy- α -methyl-2-naphthaleneacetic acid and (S)- 6-methoxy- α -methyl-2- naphthaleneacetic acid, sodium salt, respectively. Naproxen and naproxen sodium have the following structures as in the Fig 1 respectively:

Fig 1: A Chemical Structure of Naproxen Sodium.

Several methods have been reported for the estimation of naproxen in plasma using high-performance liquid chromatography. Most of these methods have time-consuming sample preparation procedures. Gopinath S et al., has reported LC MS/MS method simultaneous determination of esomeprazole and naproxen in human plasma and the run time was 4 minutes by using Solid-phase extraction method [4]. Elsinghorst PW et al., has reported LC-MS/MS method for the measurement of naproxen in human plasma using a linearity range of 0.100-50.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ with a short run time of only 2 minutes by using protein precipitation method [5]. Bilal Y et al., HPLC method has been developed and validated for the determination of naproxen 220 mg in human plasma linearity range of 0.10 and 5.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ [6]. Some other method were reported [7-18].

The objective of the present study was to develop a simple, selective and highly sensitive method by LC coupled with electrospray ionization (ESI) triple-quadrupole MS (Mass Spectrometry) for the determination of naproxen in human plasma. As the study was intended to perform bioavailability study on developed Naproxen sodium sustained release 375 mg (i.e. fast, medium and slow) and naproxen sodium marketed immediate release 500 mg. Naproxen C_{max} was in the range of 75-85 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, as the absorption of sustained release formulation expected may vary, hence the desired sensitivity achieved by using liquid chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry in the concentration range of 1.167 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ to 163.729 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The simple protein precipitation method was applied for the pre-treatment of plasma, and only 100 μL human plasma was used for the analysis. The total run time per injection was 3.0 minutes. The developed method for the plasma samples and the validated LC-MS/MS (Liquid Chromatography Mass Spectrometry/ Mass Spectrometry) analytical method were applied to a pharmacokinetic study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and reagents

Naproxen reference standard and ketoprofen internal standard were procured from Strides Arcolab Limited, Bangalore, India. Acetonitrile of HPLC grade (High Performance Liquid Chromatography) were supplied by JT becker. Fresh frozen human plasma (K_3EDTA as anticoagulant) used during validation supplied by Sai Laxmilabs Hyderabad. Water HPLC grade was obtained from a Milli-Q water purification system. Ammonium acetate HPLC grade was procured from CDH. Glacial acetic acid analytical reagent grade was procured from merck.

Instrumentation and Chromatographic Conditions

Liquid chromatography tandem-mass spectrometry was used for the method development and validation. Mass spectrometry model agilent triple quad, HPLC model agilent infinity 1290 binary pump, and auto sampler was used to keep temperature at 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, column oven used to keep temperature at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Detection was made at m/z (mass-to-charge) 229.1 / 169.0 for naproxen, m/z 253.08 / 209.0 for internal standard using esipositive ionization mode. Mass hunter 4.1 workstation software was used for the quantification. The stationary phase was Gemini C18, 50 x 4.6, 5 μm (Micrometer).

EXPERIMENTAL

Method Development and Optimization

The procedure was developed to validate a method for the determination for Naproxen in human plasma using K_3EDTA (Tripotassium Ethylene diamine tetra acetic Acid) as an anti-coagulant. The standard stock solution was diluted with Acetonitrile & methanol to 10 ng/mL (nanogram/milligram) before injecting into the Gemini C18, 50 x 4.6, 5 μm with different ratios of acetonitrile and ammonium acetate buffer. Different flow rate of 1.0, 0.8, 0.5 ml/min (milliliter/minute) were used. The optimum mobile phase was found to be acetonitrile and ammonium acetate buffer 20 mM (millimeter) (1:1 v/v) [volume/volume]. The separation was carried out by using temperature at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a flow rate of 0.8 mL. The injection volume was 5 μL and run time was 3 minutes. The retention time of analyte and internal standard was 2.054 and 1.922 minutes.

Preparation of Naproxen and Ketoprofen (Internal Standard) Stock solution

Weighed accurately, about 100.10 mg (Milligram) of naproxen and ketoprofen Working standard and transferred to a 10 mL clean glass volumetric flask, dissolved HPLC grade methanol and made up the volume with the same to produce a solution of 10 mg/mL. The internal standard stock solution was diluted to suitable concentrations (300 µg/mL) using diluent solution (acetonitrile: water (1:1) v/v). Corrected the above concentration of naproxen solution accounting for its potency, molecular weight and the actual amount weighed. A batch number was provided and the 'Stock Weighing and Solution Preparation' form was completed. The stock solution was stored in refrigerator below 2-8 °C and used for maximum of Four days.

Biological Matrix

Six K3EDTA human plasma lots were screened for selectivity test. All seven human plasma lots were found free of any significant interference for naproxen and internal standard. Three plasma lots were pooled and used to prepare calibration standards and quality control samples selectivity and sensitivity test were performed, 'Bioanalytical Method Validation' before bulk spiking. After bulk spiking, aliquots calibration curve standards and quality control samples of spiked plasma samples were pipetted out in prelabelled polypropylene RIA vials and then all the bulk spiked samples were transferred to deep freezer below -70°C, except twelve sets of QCL and QCH, which were transferred to deep freezer at -20°C for generation of stability data at -20°C.

Calibration Curve Standards and Quality Control Samples

Calibration curve standard consisting of a set of eight non-zero concentrations ranging from 1.167 µg/mL to 163.729 µg/mL for naproxen. Prepared quality control samples consisted of naproxen concentrations quality control lower limit of quantification 1.190 µg/mL (QCLLQ), quality control lower 3.494 µg/mL (QCL), quality control mid 74.393 µg/mL (QCM) and quality control high 145.581 µg/mL (QCH). These samples were stored below -70°C until use. Twelve sets of QCL and QCH were transferred to the -20 °C (minus) deep freezer to check -20°C stability. Six sets of quality control samples for dilution integrity were prepared by spiking approximately 1.75 times (254.767 µg/mL) and 3.45 times (520.255 µg/mL) of the highest standard concentration of naproxen.

Sample Preparation

The thawed samples were vortexed to ensure complete mixing of the contents. A 100 µL of the sample was pipetted into a glass test tube. 25 µL of 300 µg/mL ketoprofen, except in blank plasma sample, and vortexed. Then added 0.4 mL Acetonitrile, samples vortexed at 2000 rpm for 10 minutes and then sample centrifuged at 2000 rpm (rotation per minute) at 4 °C for 10 minutes. 300µL of the supernatant was transferred vials and injected.

Data Processing

The chromatograms were acquired and processed by peak area ratio method using the Mass hunter 4.1 workstation software. The concentration of the unknown was calculated from the following equation using regression analysis of spiked standard with the reciprocal of the ratio of the (drug concentration)² to internal standard concentration as a weighing factor (1/x²):

$$y = mx + c$$

Where,

y = peak area ratio of naproxen to internal standard

m = slope of calibration curve

x = concentration of Naproxen

c = y-axis intercept of the calibration curve

Validation Parameters

Validation is a process which involves confirmation or establishment by laboratory studies that a method / procedure / system / analyst can give the required accuracy, precision, sensitivity, ruggedness, etc. In the most basic form, validation of an analytical procedure demonstrates that the procedure developed is suitable for its intended purpose. Validation of the method was carried out after the development of the LCMS (Liquid Chromatography Mass Spectrometry) methods. Performed the following validation parameters as per the USFDA (United State Food and Drug Administration) guidelines i.e. specificity / selectivity, carry over, linearity, precision & accuracy, recovery, dilution integrity, ruggedness, stabilities like freeze thaw stability, bench top stability, long term stability, stock solution stability (stock dilution and stock solution stability)^[3]

System Suitability

Prepared aqueous mixture of QCM concentration for an analyte and intended internal standard. Injected six replicates of aqueous mixture of QCM concentration of analyte and internal standard by using chromatographic conditions. Recorded the retention time of analyte and internal standard and the peak area ratio of analyte to internal standard. Calculated the Mean, Standard Deviation (s.d.) and Coefficient of Variation (% CV) of retention time of the analyte and internal standard and Peak area ratio.

Acceptance criteria: % CV for peak area ratio should be $\leq 2\%$ & % CV for retention time should be $\leq 4\%$.

The system suitability was performed before starting each activities and it was in-line with acceptance criteria less than or equal to 2 % (percentage) for area ratio and less than or equal to 4 % for retention time.

Specificity / Selectivity

Specificity and selectivity were evaluated by analyzing a total of six different lots of plasma and they were extracted and analyzed for the assessment of potential interferences with endogenous substances. Spiked one aliquot of each blank sample with the analyte at LLOQ level and with working solution of internal standard and other aliquot as blank sample. Analyzed all spiked and blank samples. Specificity and selectivity were performed from six different lots of plasma and they were extracted and analyzed for the assessment of potential interferences with endogenous substances. The specificity will be evaluated by comparing the responses of interfering peak at the retention time of drug and internal standard in the standard blank against the response of the respective extracted LLOQ.

Matrix Effect

Blank samples (plasma) from six independent sources of matrix were processed in duplicate and then spiked with analyte at QCL and QCH level and internal standard at the concentration used in the method being validated just before injection into the LC-MS/MS. An aqueous solution of analyte was prepared at QCL and QCH with internal standard in diluent. Peak area ratios of the plasma samples were compared with that of reference solution to ensure that the matrix factor was consistent for different sources of matrix.

Signal to Noise Ratio

Signal to Noise ratio was determined at the LLOQ (lower limit of quantification) from the chromatogram by comparing the area obtained at LLOQ for each lot used in the specificity / selectivity experiment with area obtained in respective blank samples.

Carry Over

Carry over is calculated as the percentage peak area observed in a processed blank plasma injected immediately after a processed injected Blank, 2LLOQ and 2ULOQ (upper limit of quantification) samples.

Linearity

Linearity established by preparing an eight-point standard calibration curve in K3EDTA human plasma covering the naproxen concentration range from 1.167 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ to 163.729 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ using ketoprofen as internal standard. Three accepted precision and accuracy batches were analyzed in this range. Calibration curves were calculated by least square linear regression analysis of the response ratios (Analyte/Internal standard) in the calibration standards using a weighting factor of $1/X^2$. Back calculated concentrations of naproxen in calibration standards were determined using the best fit regression curve calculated for each batch.

Recovery

Prepared 6 sets of recovery comparison samples by spiking 5 μL of dilution of quality control samples (QCL, QCM, QCH) of Naproxen, 25 μL of internal standard dilution (approx. 300 ng/mL) and 300 μL of diluent, representing 100 % extraction and injected. The recovery comparison samples of naproxen were compared against extracted samples of QCL, QCM and QCH samples of PA-2 (Precision and Accuracy-2) batch.

Dilution Integrity

Twelve sets of dilution integrity samples were prepared by spiking approximately 1.75 times (254.767 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and 3.45 times (520.255 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) of the highest standard concentration. Six sets of dilution integrity samples were processed by diluting them twice and another six sets by diluting them four times using pooled plasma. These quality control samples were analyzed along with a freshly spiked and processed calibration curve standards. The quality control sample concentrations were calculated using appropriate dilution factor.

Re-injection Reproducibility

Reinjection reproducibility is performed to establish that the reinjection of the samples kept in the auto sampler at controlled temperature has no effect on the result reproducibility. One precision and accuracy batch PA-1 (Precision and Accuracy-1) was retained in the autosampler at 5°C for 27 hours to test the re-injection reproducibility of the method. Reinjection reproducibility concentrations were compared against the PA-3 (Precision and Accuracy-3) batch concentrations. The autosampler stability sample analysis results were used for re-injection reproducibility calculations.

Freeze-Thaw Stability Three Cycles

The stability in human plasma was determined for three freeze-thaw cycles. Six replicates of QCL and QCH were analyzed after undergoing three freeze-thaw cycles (at both $-70^{\circ}\text{C} \pm (\text{plus or minus}) 20^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-20^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ storage temperatures). The stability was determined by calculating the percentage nominal of QCL and QCH samples against freshly spiked and prepared calibration curve Standards.

Bench Top Stability

Six replicates of QCL and QCH samples were processed after keeping the samples on bench for about 11 hours. Bench top stability were assessed by calculating percent nominal at QCL and QCH level against freshly spiked and prepared calibration curve Standards.

Long Term Stability at below -20°C and -70°C

To assess the stability of the analyte in the biological matrix under the same conditions of storage as that of the study samples the following test was performed. Six samples of each quality control samples at low and high concentrations were stored below -20°C and -70°C in the freezer for 5 days. These samples were quantified against the freshly spiked calibration curve standards and % change calculated against fresh quality control samples.

Stock Dilution Stability

The stability of stock dilutions of analyte and the internal standard was evaluated at room temperature. Aqueous stock dilutions of the analyte and the internal standard were prepared. One portion of the stock dilution was placed in the refrigerator between $2-8^{\circ}\text{C}$, while the other portion was placed at room temperature for 48 hours.

Stock Solution Stability

Stock solution stability was carried out for 3 days by injecting six replicates of stock dilution of stability standards (analyte and internal standard which prepared and stored in the refrigerator between $2-8^{\circ}\text{C}$) and freshly prepared stock dilutions of comparison standard (analyte and internal standard). The response of stability sample was corrected by multiplying with correction factor.

Ruggedness

One precision and Accuracy batch was performed with different column of same make and with different analyst.

Pharmacokinetic study design

The protocol was approved by independent ethics committee before the study. All the subjects explained about the study procedures in both verbal and written. Before they take part, the subjects were asked to sign the Informed Consent Form. Following oral administration of one tablet of naproxen sodium 375 mg sustained release tablets and naproxen Sodium 500 mg tablet (marketed immediate release) by oral route. A series of venous blood samples of 3.5 mL will be collected into labelled vacutainers tubes containing anticoagulant. The baseline pre-dose sample will be taken within one hour prior to dosing. After dosing, samples will be taken at the following intervals 0.0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, 5.5, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0, 12.0, 16.0 and 24.0 hours post-dose. Blood samples were centrifuged at $10 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and at 2500-3000 rpm for 10 minutes. The separated plasma were transferred to pre-labelled polypropylene tubes. All plasma samples will be stored in an upright position below -30°C until completion of analysis. Plasma concentration-time profile were obtained by using Phoenix software 6.4.0.768 version.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The positive ion scans of standard solutions of naproxen and ketoprofen had protonated molecular ions analyzed under positive ionization condition (M+H) of m/z 229.1 and 253.08, respectively. Fragmentation of these ions using collision induced dissociation at collision energies ramped from 5 to 130V resulted in strong product ions for at naproxen m/z 169.0 and 209.0, for ketoprofen. Under the chromatographic conditions the transition of $229.1 \rightarrow 169.0$ and $253.08 \rightarrow 209.0$ were selected for optimal monitoring of Naproxen and IS (internal standard), respectively. The ion spray voltage at 5000V (voltage) provided a sufficient response under the selected chromatographic conditions, and no further increase in the response was found when the ion spray voltage was increased further. Peak top noise was found at a lower interface temperature of 500°C , and by increasing the temperature to 550°C it was reduced and yielded a smoother. The mobile phase yielded retention times of less than 3 minutes for all sample allowing high sample throughput. No significant interferences were observed at the retention times of analyte and internal standard for all the six batch screened. The IS-normalized matrix factor was found to be 0.9520 for QCL and 0.9832 for QCH (close to unity) for six different matrix lots for Naproxen was % CV was 0.97 for QCL and 1.12 for QCH. The signal-to-noise ratio obtained for the samples was greater than 5 for all the plasma lots tested. The % carry over was found to be 0.00 for analyte and 0.00 for internal standard. A regression equation with a weighting factor of $1/(\text{concentration ratio})^2$ of drug to IS concentration was judged to produce the best fit for the concentration-detector response relationship for naproxen in human plasma. Correlation coefficient (r^2) was greater than 0.9974 in the concentration range of $1.167 \mu\text{g/mL}$ to $163.729 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for Naproxen. The precision of the assay was measured by the percent coefficient of variation over the concentration range of QCL, QCH and QCM samples respectively during the course of validation. The accuracy of the assay was defined as the absolute value of the ratio of the calculated mean values of the LLOQ, low, middle and high quality control samples to their respective nominal values, expressed in percentage presented in the Table. 1-4. No statistical outlier was found.

Table 1: Intraday Precision and Accuracy of Naproxen.

	Parameters	QCLLQ	QCL	QCM	QCH
Precision and Accuracy-1	Mean	102.18	103.02	99.47	100.85
	% CV	4.97	6.59	1.94	1.10
Precision and Accuracy – 2	Mean	105.29	101.26	103.39	101.08
	% CV	4.16	6.33	2.71	1.01

Table 2: Global (PA1 & PA2) of Naproxen.

Parameters	QCLLQ	QCL	QCM	QCH
Mean	101.9	102.15	103.41	102.73
% CV	6.67	4.04	2.03	1.04

Table 3: Interday precision and Accuracy of Naproxen.

Parameters	QCLLQ	QCL	QCM	QCH
Mean	101.9	102.15	103.41	102.73
% CV	6.67	4.04	2.03	1.04

Table 4: Between Batch Precision and Accuracy of Naproxen.

Parameters	QCLLQ	QCL	QCM	QCH
Mean	103.13	102.15	102.09	101.55
% CV	5.25	5.47	2.83	1.3

The recovery of analyte and internal standard refer Table 5 & 6. The mean recovery of internal standard was 52.57 %.

Table 5: Recovery of the Analyte.

Parameter	QCL		QCM		QCH	
	Unextracted sample Peak Area	Extracted sample Peak Area	Unextracted sample Peak Area	Extracted sample Peak Area	Unextracted sample Peak Area	Extracted sample Peak Area
% CV	11.29	1.28	2.78	0.94	0.24	2.59
% Recovery	54.18		51.76		50.50	
Over all % Recovery	52.15					

Table 6: Recovery of the Internal Standard.

Parameter	Unextracted sample Peak Area	Extracted sample Peak Area
% CV	0.75	1.91
% Recovery	52.57	

The within batch precision and accuracy, for a dilution factor of 2 was 3.89 % and 103.61 %. The within batch precision and accuracy, for a dilution factor of 4 was 1.93 % and 102.48 %. The mean accuracy for reinjection reproducibility ranged from 100.26 % (QCM) to 103.50 % (QCLLQ) and the precision ranged from 0.83 % (QCH) to 5.47 % (QCLLQ). The percent nominal ranged from 95.92 % to 101.45 % and precision ranged from 1.47 % to 6.85 % and percent change ranged from 1.18 to 2.03. The percent nominal for freeze-thaw cycles ranged from 100.44 % to 102.91% and precision ranged from 1.49 % to 5.22 % and percent change ranged from 0.31 to 1.57. The percent nominal for bench top stability ranged from 95.92 % to 101.45% and precision ranged from 1.47 % to 6.85 % and percent change ranged from 1.13 to 2.03. The percent nominal for long term stability at below -20° C ranged from 100.34 % to 101.80 % and the precision ranged from 1.98 % to 7.03 % and percent change ranged from 0.73 to 1.46. The percent nominal for long term stability at below -20° C and -70° C ranged from 98.63 % to 100.97 % and precision ranged from 1.53 % to 4.32 % and percent change ranged 0.64 to 1.93. The percent change of stability of stock dilutions for Naproxen was 0.93 % and for Ketoprofen is 0.57 %. The percent change of stock solution stability of analyte and the internal standard for naproxen was 0.77 % and for ketoprofen is 0.67 %. The mean accuracy for ruggedness ranged from 98.57 % (QCLLQ) to 101.08 % (QCH) and the precision ranged from 1.92 % (QCM) to 5.79 % (QCLLQ).

Chromatography

Representative chromatograms of blank plasma, QCLLQ, QCL, QCM, QCH and calibration curve of Naproxen given in Fig.2 to 12.

Fig 2: A Representative Chromatogram of a Blank Plasma (Naproxen).

Fig 3: A Representative Chromatogram of a Blank Plasma (Internal Standard).

Fig. 4: A Representative Chromatogram of a QCLLQ (Naproxen).

Fig. 5: A Representative Chromatogram of a QCLLQ (Internal Standard).

Fig. 6: A Representative Chromatogram of a QCL (Naproxen).

Fig. 7: A Representative Chromatogram of a QCL (Internal Standard).

Fig. 8: A Representative Chromatogram of a QCM (Naproxen).

Fig. 9: A Representative Chromatogram of a QCM (Internal Standard).

Fig. 10: A Representative Chromatogram of a QCH (Naproxen).

Fig. 11: A Representative Chromatogram of a QCH (Internal Standard).

Fig 12: A Representative Calibration Curve for Regression Analysis.

Pharmacokinetic study result

To verify the validated method in an actual situation, human plasma samples were collected from six healthy male volunteers and estimated by using LCMS-MS, pharmacokinetic calculation performed by using Phoenix software 6.4.0.768 version. The mean pharmacokinetic parameters for the four formulations in fasting condition are tabulated in Table 7. The Mean plasma concentration-time profile of Naproxen for all formulations are presented in Fig. 13. The release and absorption significantly higher with the test drug compared to reference drug for T_{max} , C_{max} and AUC. However, the sustained release formulation exhibited a longer elimination half-life ($t_{1/2}$) than the immediate release tablet, thus indicating the sustained release properties are similar to the reference formulation.

Table 7: Mean Pharmacokinetic Parameters of Naproxen Sodium Marketed Immediate Release and Sustained Release Tablet (Fast, Medium & Slow).

Formulation	Kel (1/hr)	Half life (hour)	Tmax (hr)	Cmax (ug/mL)	AUClast (hr*ug/mL)	AUCINF (hr*ug/mL)	MRTlast (hr)
Immediate Release Tablet	0.350	2.203	1.833	54.209	144.237	147.483	3.299
Fast Sustained Release Tablet	0.109	0.883	0.258	10.685	35.146	36.265	0.275
Medium Sustained Release Tablet	0.186	3.840	2.167	73.767	301.557	307.561	4.954
Slow Sustained Release Tablet	0.030	0.776	0.258	4.889	8.145	7.775	0.327
Immediate Release Tablet	0.134	5.464	2.667	68.879	373.548	391.273	6.416
Fast Sustained Release Tablet	0.039	1.230	0.258	4.562	73.928	82.259	0.447
Medium Sustained Release Tablet	0.192	3.722	3.583	63.199	383.289	391.499	6.466
Slow Sustained Release Tablet	0.038	0.710	0.376	3.141	64.036	69.217	1.201

C_{max} =Maximum plasma concentration

T_{max} =Time of the maximum plasma concentration.

AUClast: area under the plasma concentration-time curve from time zero to the time of the last quantifiable concentration,

AUCinf: area under the plasma concentration-time curve from time zero extrapolated to the infinite time

Kel= elimination rate constant

MRTlast= Mean residence time from the time of dosing to the time of last quantifiable concentration.

Fig 13: Mean Plasma Concentration-Time Profile of Naproxen Sodium Marketed Immediate Release and Sustained Release Tablet (Fast, Medium & Slow).

CONCLUSION

The data provided in the article is of accurate, precise and reliable measurement of Naproxen concentrations in human plasma by using LCMS/MS after oral administration of 550 (Immediate Release) and 375 mg (Modified Release) to healthy volunteers. The method chosen is fast, robust, and sensitive. Each sample requires less than 3 min run time. The assay method is also highly specific due to the intrinsic selectivity of tandem mass spectrometry. The precision and accuracy are within the recommended limits in this concentration range. Hence the contemporary exploration established by representing the significant analytical work was successfully used for the naproxen estimation by LCMS-MS method in human plasma for pharmacokinetic studies. The simplicity of sample preparation and the short chromatographic runtime give the technique ability for high sample throughput. From the outcome it can be concluded that the present method is useful for pharmacokinetic/bioequivalence studies with desired precision and accuracy. Future work shall be carried out to reduce the concentration range.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express the gratitude to the management of Srinivas College of Pharmacy, SeQuent Research Limited & Strides Arcolab Ltd., for providing necessary support to carry out the work.

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